

Business Incubation as a Catalyst: Examining the Impact of Entrepreneurial Education on Entrepreneurial Intention in Emerging Contexts

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Abstract

Background: Entrepreneurial education (EE) and institutional support mechanisms such as Business Incubation Programmes (BIPs) play critical roles in shaping entrepreneurial intentions among university students. However, in Bangladesh, the relationship between EE, BIPs, and Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) remains underexplored, particularly from the perspective of resource-based and behavioural theories.

Objective: Grounded in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and drawing on the Resource-Based View (RBV), this study examines the role of BIPs in amplifying the impact of EE on EI among business students in Bangladeshi universities.

Methodology: The study employed a quantitative research design, utilising a structured questionnaire administered to 388 business students from four leading universities in Dhaka. Data were analysed using SmartPLS 4.1.0.9 and SPSS 27 to test the proposed model and hypotheses.

Results: The findings reveal that EE and BIP have a positive and significant influence on EI. Moreover, BIP substantially moderates the relationship between EE and EI, indicating that incubation programmes strengthen the effect of educational inputs on students' entrepreneurial intentions.

Conclusion: Integrating entrepreneurial education with institutional support mechanisms such as incubation programmes fosters a stronger entrepreneurial mindset and intention among students.

Unique contribution: This study enriches entrepreneurship literature by integrating TPB and RBV perspectives to explain how cognitive and resource-based factors jointly shape entrepreneurial intention in an emerging South Asian economy. It also provides practical implications for educators, policymakers, and ecosystem stakeholders seeking to address graduate unemployment through entrepreneurship development.

Key Recommendation: Universities should integrate business incubation Programmes with entrepreneurship education to provide practical support and enhance students' entrepreneurial readiness.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Education; Business Incubation Programmes; Entrepreneurial Intention; Theory of Planned Behaviour; Resource-Based View; Bangladesh

Introduction

Unemployment among young people is a significant and persistent challenge in Bangladesh, with substantial social and economic implications for a country with a rapidly growing educated young population. Approximately 47% of university graduates are unemployed one year after graduation (World Bank, 2024). It signifies the disconnection between higher education and labour market absorption. In this context, entrepreneurship is increasingly recognized not merely as a route to

self-employment but as a powerful driver of innovation, job creation, and sustainable economic growth. This is particularly pertinent for business students who, through their education, are expected to possess foundational knowledge of economics, strategic management, and market dynamics. Although entrepreneurship is emphasised in national development agendas and embedded within university curricula, entrepreneurial intention (EI) among business students in Bangladesh remains comparatively low. This paradox, 'high exposure to EE but low entrepreneurial endeavour', examines whether the current pedagogical and institutional frameworks are genuinely effective in fostering entrepreneurial development.

Entrepreneurship education is one of the strongest predictors and has been traditionally viewed as one of the main drivers of EI. This gives students the knowledge, skills, and cognitive ideas to identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities (Al-Qadasi et al., 2024). Empirical evidence on the effectiveness of entrepreneurial education (EE) remains inconclusive, particularly in developing countries, where programs often lack sufficient practical components and skills training necessary to translate knowledge into entrepreneurial practice. (Hosen & Habib, 2024). The reality is that entrepreneurial intentions often fail to materialise, mainly due to limited access to physical support infrastructures, inadequate exposure, and insufficient opportunities for experiential learning (Saeed et al., 2018).

Recent research has suggested Business Incubation Programs (BIPs) might be a promising approach to filling this void (Anjum et al., 2024). These types of programs, which typically provide targeted support including mentorship, networking, financial assistance, and access to resources, have positively affected entrepreneurial outcomes in various settings (Hackett & Dilts, 2004). Although the direct effect of BIPs on EI is widely recognized, a growing stream of the literature proposes that BIPs may act as pivotal moderators (either strengthening or weakening) of the relationships between entrepreneurship education and shaping intention.

Despite valuable insights into Business Incubation Programs (BIPs), empirical studies examining their dual role as both a direct predictor and a moderating factor remain scarce, particularly within the Bangladeshi context. However, prior studies have often overlooked the multifaceted relationship between government support and the educational environment. Instead, they rely on varying instrumentation methods to evaluate the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial disposition, frequently treating both as independent antecedents rather than examining whether entrepreneurial education or school support serves as an antecedent to the other. In addition, there is limited research in academic literature concerning the rise and spread of Bangladesh's university-affiliated incubation centre and start-up hub ecosystem. The current paper aims to fill this critical theoretical gap by developing and testing a model based on moderation (see Fig. 1), in which BIPs directly influence EI and moderate EE's influence on EI. Doing so adds a more sophisticated understanding of the interplay between educational and institutional channels in shaping entrepreneurship. These findings are important for policy-makers, curriculum developers, and support system infrastructure providers trying to promote university student entrepreneurship in developing countries.

Theoretical framework and hypotheses development

Underpinning theory

The present investigation is carried out based on a comprehensive theoretical framework that incorporates the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) and the Resource-Based View (RBV) (Barney, 1991) in explicating the factors that determine entrepreneurial intention (EI) in university business students in Bangladesh. According to TPB, EI is influenced by personal attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioural control. Entrepreneurial education (EE) develops these cognitive components by fostering opportunity awareness, positive attitudes, and self-efficacy through knowledge and skill acquisition. However, cognitive readiness alone often fails to translate into actionable intention without a supportive, experiential environment. RBV holds explanatory power in this area, suggesting that access to rare, valuable, and inimitable resources leads to strategic benefits that facilitate entrepreneurial involvement. Business incubation programs (BIPs) are one such asset that provides the ecosystem with crucial mentorship, networking, capital, and facilities (Hackett & Dilts, 2004). As an independent variable, BIP is expected to directly enhance EI by improving students' resource base and perceived control. Furthermore, in line with TPB and RBV, BIPs are suggested to moderate the EE–EI relationship by translating educational inputs into usable entrepreneurial motivation. This combined TPB–RBV model thus offers a robust, testable framework for understanding how cognitive and resource-based factors jointly shape entrepreneurial intention, especially in Bangladesh as an emerging entrepreneurial landscape.

Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial education (EE) has emerged as a key pedagogical and policy tool to foster entrepreneurial orientation and promote venture creation, particularly in academic settings. Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), EE is supposed to exert its impact on entrepreneurial intention (EI) through attitudes, social norms, and self-efficacy. Exposure to entrepreneurial role models and structured coursework strengthens students' cognitive foundations while fostering risk-taking and opportunity recognition, which are the key drivers of entrepreneurial intention. EE also validates entrepreneurship as a career alternative, enhancing the social acceptability in the collectivist societies like Bangladesh (Tripopsakul, 2025). In addition, by developing skills, increasing confidence, and capabilities, EE strengthens perceived behavioural control (Tripopsakul, 2025). Empirical studies across contexts confirm a positive relationship between EE and EI though its strength varies by context. In Bangladesh, EE presents a vital mechanism for addressing unemployment through self-employment and innovation. Thus, it is proposed that:

H1: Entrepreneurial education positively influences entrepreneurial intention.

Business Incubation Programs and Entrepreneurial Intention

Business Incubation Programs (BIPs) have developed as strategic institutional mechanisms to promote aspiring entrepreneurs through coaching, facilities, and a business-friendly environment. BIPs enhance entrepreneurial capacity by providing resources that are most likely valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) (Barney, 1991) according to the Resource-Based

View. For instance, Ravichandran and Dixit (2024) highlight that BIPs offer infrastructure, technical support, networking opportunities, seed funding, and mentoring resources, collectively reducing entry barriers and mitigating perceived risks. Derived from the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), BIPs also increase perceived behavioural control by developing self-efficacy and the confidence to start and maintain a venture. Practical evidence indicates that incubation environments significantly strengthen entrepreneurs' confidence, enhance their ability to recognize opportunities, and accelerate business development. (Akpoviro et al., 2021). Given Bangladesh's structural and financial barriers (Rana et al., 2024), BIPs can encourage students' entrepreneurial intentions with their educational and training support. Accordingly, we hypothesize that access to business incubation enhances entrepreneurial intention.

H2: Business incubation programs positively influence entrepreneurial intention.

The Moderating Role of Business Incubation Programs

The importance of entrepreneurial education (EE) for stimulating entrepreneurial intention has received widespread attention, but its efficacy is contingent upon supportive institutional frameworks promoting action. Business Incubation Programs (BIPs) are crucial enablers that provide a platform for promising entrepreneurs with resources, mentorship, and a live learning experience. Following the resource-based view (Barney, 1991), BIPs offer strategic resources that cannot be found in pure classroom-based instruction, such as seed money, legal and technical assistance, business connections, and real-life validation, fostering the practical viability of start-ups. Meanwhile, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) highlights that entrepreneurial intention is influenced by attitudes, norms, and perceived behavioural control. While EE improves cognitive readiness and attitudes, BIPs can amplify EE's impact by fostering students' self-efficacy and strengthening perceived behavioural control (Anjum et al., 2024). BIPs can therefore be seen as a moderating process that enhances the EE–EI relationship by engaging students in entrepreneurial ecosystems with access to feedback and experience. Such support is crucial in developing countries such as Bangladesh, where viable entrepreneurial ecosystems are still being made. Accordingly, this study proposes that Business Incubation Programs (BIPs) moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial education (EE) and entrepreneurial intention (EI), amplifying the impact of EE when incubation support is available.

H3: Business incubation programs moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention.

Figure 1: Research Model Method

Measure

All measurement scales used in the current study were obtained from previously established sources. A back-translation technique was employed to ensure linguistic and conceptual equivalence between the original and translated questionnaires. Participants had to indicate their agreement on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). In particular, entrepreneurship education (EE) was measured using six items borrowed from Hasan et al. (2017). The business incubation program (BIP) was assessed using six items extracted from Sahban et al. (2014). Finally, entrepreneurial intention (EI) is adopted from six items initially developed by Liñán and Chen (2006). Appendix 1 presents the detailed items for all measurement scales used in this study.

Sample and data collection

This research focuses on university students from the business studies field who have attended entrepreneurial education and training programmes. Business students should possess basic business knowledge and an understanding of its application in entrepreneurial alternatives. When education is structured in a practical sense, they are also more predisposed to being entrepreneurial. Since the study centred on entrepreneurial intention, this group is highly pertinent.

Four of Dhaka's most popular business schools, the University of Dhaka, Jagannath University, North South University, and BRAC University, were chosen as the data source. Surveys were administered at the beginning of the class period, and participation was voluntary. Respondents were given 20 minutes to complete the survey and offered a small incentive for their participation. This approach ensured a supportive, participatory environment for effective data collection.

The survey took place in March/April 2025, and 450 business students participated. Among them, 412 questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 91.55%. However, 24 responses were rejected because they had blank or partial entries. As a result, to ensure data quality and consistency, 388 fully completed and valid responses were included in the final dataset. A total of

388 (n = 205, 52.83% females; n = 183, 47.16% males) responded to the survey. Regarding subjects' ages, the mean is slightly over 21.5, with the mode, 43.29% of the responses (n = 168), being 21-23; 32.47% (n = 126) below 24, and 24.22% (n = 94) between 18 and 20. With respect to the students' academic year, 34.27% (n = 133) were third-year students, 28.86% (n = 112) were second-year students, 19.58% (n = 76) were fourth-year students, and 17.26% (n = 67) were first-year students. These demographic data indicated a diverse and representative sample of university students.

Data analysis

The current study assesses the research model using a structured four-step approach. The questionnaire was prepared, and data were collected first. Reliability and validity in the measurement model, Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and factor loadings were examined in the second step. Third, discriminant validity was assessed using SmartPLS 4.1.0.9 to verify the distinctiveness of the constructs. Eventually, the hypotheses were tested using PLS-SEM. To examine the significance of the path coefficients, we use a bootstrapping method with 5,000 resamples in SmartPLS. Supplementary statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 27.0.

Findings

Common Method Bias

To mitigate concerns associated with CMB, which can arise from systematic measurement error, this study employed Harman's single-factor test and principal axis factoring to examine the presence of CMB. This analysis aligns with previous research on standard method variance. Following Harman's advice, CMB is possible if one factor explains more than 50% of the variance (Harman, 1976). The present analysis revealed that for the first factor, the amount of variance accounted for was only 29.63%, which is lower than the critical threshold. As a result, these findings suggest that common method bias is not a significant concern in the data.

Measurement Model assessment

For factor validity and reliability, PLS-SEM was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of Hair et al. (2019). Cronbach's alpha (α) was used to estimate internal consistency, and values of $\alpha \geq 0.7$ were considered satisfactory reliability. All three items scored better than the cut-off point (see Table 1). Composite Reliability (CR) was also examined, and all CR scores were greater than 0.7; thus, construct reliability was supported (Ringle et al., 2023). Indicator reliability was confirmed by OLVs, where loadings of 0.708 or higher are considered acceptable; all items met this criterion (see Table 1). Convergent validity was analysed with Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with values >0.5 indicating acceptable validity; all the constructs satisfied this criterion (Hair et al., 2019; Ringle et al., 2023).

Discriminant validity was assessed using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT), Fornell-Larcker criterion, and cross loadings. All the HTMT values in Table 2 are < 0.85 , demonstrating good discriminant validity. The Fornell-Larcker criterion also indicated that the square root of AVE of each construct was greater than its relationships with other constructs (Table 2), thus the evidence for discriminant validity was established. Table 3 showed cross-loadings, demonstrating that items

were loaded most strongly on the scale of their hypothesised construct (bold values). In general, the findings from HTMT, Fornell-Larcker, and cross-loadings reveal evidence of strong discriminant validity for the measurement model.

Table 1: Reliability and Validity Scores

Variable	Items	α	CR	AVE	VIF	λ
Entrepreneurial Education	EE1	0.845	0.845	0.563	1.750	0.758
	EE2				1.857	0.774
	EE3				1.824	0.780
	EE4				1.726	0.753
	EE5				1.604	0.710
	EE6				1.559	0.726
Business Incubation Program	BIP1	0.844	0.850	0.562	1.649	0.719
	BIP2				1.643	0.721
	BIP3				2.005	0.803
	BIP4				1.511	0.725
	BIP5				1.511	0.780
	BIP6				1.723	0.788
Entrepreneurial Intention	EI1	0.846	0.853	0.567	1.442	0.845
	EI2				1.682	0.745
	EI3				1.733	0.722
	EI4				1.910	0.792
	EI5				1.924	0.778
	EI6				1.954	0.777

Note: N=400; VIF = Variance Inflation Factor, CR = Composite reliability, α = Cronbach’s alpha, AVE = Average variance extracted, λ =Outer loading.

Table 2: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) and Fornell-Larcker criterion scores

The matrix of HTMT				Fornell-Larcker Criterion			
	BIP	EE	EI	BIP x EE	BIP	EE	EI
BIP					0.750		
EE	0.634				0.536	0.751	
EI	0.686	0.690			0.588	0.588	0.753
BIP x EE	0.079	0.262	0.281				

Table 3: Cross-loading scores

	BIP	EE	EI
BIP1	0.719	0.367	0.385
BIP2	0.721	0.354	0.406
BIP3	0.803	0.396	0.442
BIP4	0.680	0.376	0.397
BIP5	0.780	0.463	0.503

BIP6	0.788	0.441	0.491
EE1	0.392	0.758	0.434
EE2	0.305	0.774	0.441
EE3	0.322	0.780	0.465
EE4	0.540	0.753	0.446
EE5	0.544	0.710	0.424
EE6	0.321	0.726	0.436
EI1	0.424	0.333	0.645
EI2	0.366	0.457	0.745
EI3	0.525	0.492	0.772
EI4	0.489	0.486	0.792
EI5	0.417	0.445	0.778
EI6	0.414	0.421	0.777

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the structural model

Structural model analysis and hypothesis testing

When interpreting the structural model, we considered multicollinearity through VIF values, checked the significance of path coefficients by bootstrapping, and examined effect sizes (f^2) and model predictive power. VIF values for the Inner-Model were between 1.068 and 1.492; in the Outer-Model, the VIFs were less than 3. The VIF values are shown in Table 1. These findings indicate that the data do not have major multicollinearity issues (Hair et al., 2019). Additionally, the R^2 value of 0.470 (see Fig. 2) for the dependent variable (EI) indicates that the predictors in our model explain about 47% of the variance in the dependent variable. The remaining variance may be attributed to factors not covered in this study. As per Hair et al. (2019) guidelines, the obtained R^2 value of 0.470 for EI reflects moderate explanatory power.

Table 4: Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
BIP -> EI	0.395	0.397	0.043	9.137	0.000	Supported
EE -> EI	0.340	0.342	0.044	7.723	0.000	Supported
BIP x EE -> EI	0.131	0.130	0.038	3.428	0.001	Supported

Fig. 3. Simple slope analysis.

The structural path coefficients for both direct and interaction effects of BIP and EE on EI are presented in Table 4. BIP significantly and positively impacts EI ($\beta = 0.395$, $t = 9.137$, $p < 0.001$), motivating graduate students' entrepreneurial intentions. The results also show that EE significantly and positively affects EI ($\beta = 0.340$, $t = 7.723$, $p < 0.001$). The interaction effect of BIP and EE on entrepreneurial intention (EI) is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.131$, $t = 3.428$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting that BIP significantly moderates the relationship between EE and EI. Figure 3 visually demonstrates interaction with three different trend lines green, blue, and red for different levels of BIP. Specifically, the green line is the relation at a high level of BIP, the blue line represents the relation at an average level, and the red line shows the relation at a low level of BIP. The visual trends show that the positive impact of EE on EI becomes a more substantial influence with the increase of BIP. Within the Bangladeshi context, where unemployment rates among graduates remain high and entrepreneurial activity is often constrained by resource scarcity, incubators provide critical enablers such as mentorship, seed funding, networking opportunities, and access to co-working facilities. These resources reduce uncertainty, mitigate risk perceptions, and transform theoretical learning into actionable strategies, motivating students to pursue entrepreneurial careers. For instance, initiatives like Startup Bangladesh and university-based incubation hubs have demonstrated that structured mentorship and market linkage support substantially enhance students' confidence in launching ventures. Thus, the results highlight that policy interventions and program designs emphasizing incubation support are indispensable for

converting the outcomes of EE into tangible entrepreneurial intentions, ultimately contributing to graduate employability and the broader national agenda of building a knowledge-driven, entrepreneurial economy.

The f^2 value for the paths between EE and BIP and EI, and $BIP \times EE$ and EI are 0.020 (small), 0.503 (large), 0.162 (medium), respectively. We also measured the predictive validity of specific dependent constructs within the structural framework. The predictive significance was assessed by measuring the Q^2 values. Q^2 values for BIP, EE, and EI are 0.388, 0.387, and 0.389, respectively. The model demonstrated adequate predictive relevance (because they were higher than 0). In addition, since the values were within the range of 0.25 to 0.50, the PLS-path model was found to exhibit moderate predictive relevance (Hair et al., 2019). These findings highlight a complementary relationship between institutional support and academic education in shaping entrepreneurial mindsets. The interaction effect emerges as particularly significant, revealing a strong dimension of synergy between entrepreneurial education and incubation programs. This result is consistent with the principles of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), which underscores the role of integrated influences in shaping intention and behaviour. Overall, the evidence points to the need for a coherent entrepreneurial ecosystem within higher education contexts, where classroom learning and institutional support mechanisms work in tandem to foster entrepreneurial potential.

Discussion

Present research enriches the existing body of knowledge on the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Bangladesh, particularly about university business graduates. The significant association between the constructs EE, BIP, and EI underscores the pillars that shape the ecosystem for realizing the entrepreneurial potentials in a developing country. In particular, given the positive association between EE and EI (H1), structured and curriculum-based entrepreneurial education emerges as a critical driver in fostering entrepreneurial intentions among graduates. This assertion is further reinforced by the empirical findings of Lu et al. (2021). This implies that a stronger focus on EE is essential for nurturing entrepreneurial intentions. Within the Bangladeshi higher education sector, it reflects a growing acknowledgment that students must be equipped with theoretical insights and the practical competencies necessary to translate ideas into entrepreneurial action.

Moreover, the positive impact of BIP on EI (H2) emphasises the critical role of supportive institutional mechanisms in the Ecosystem. This finding aligns with the work of Korejo et al. (2023), who argue that business incubators provide the necessary infrastructure, mentorship, networking opportunities, and access to capital that collectively stimulate entrepreneurial intention. The acceptance of H3, where BIP moderates the relationship between EE and EI, resonates with earlier findings (Saeed et al., 2018). BIP emerges as one of the most robust predictors for predicting entrepreneurial intention, suggesting that while entrepreneurship often begins with education, the translation of knowledge into intention is substantially strengthened by incubation programs. This moderating effect suggests that EE is more effective when combined with practical and experiential learning opportunities provided by BIPs. The implications of these combined findings suggest a systemic and Ecosystem approach to entrepreneurship development in Bangladesh. They advocate for greater partnership among academic institutions, government,

and private sector incubators to help create an enabling environment for young graduates to support themselves outside the classroom. Scaling and adding such programs could help tackle the core problem of graduate unemployment and revitalise the latent entrepreneurial capabilities of Bangladesh's youth.

Theoretical Implications of this study

This study integrates the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the Resource-Based View (RBV) to explain entrepreneurial intention (EI) formation among Bangladeshi business graduates. Linking EE to TPB constructs attitudes, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms confirms EE's role in shaping cognitive precursors of intention in South Asia. Simultaneously, RBV frames business incubator programs (BIP) as strategic resources that offer rare, costly, and inimitable benefits that enhance entrepreneurial capability. The moderating effect of BIP on the EE–EI relationship underscores that intention formation is both cognitive and resource-dependent. This dual-theory model advances the field by illustrating the interplay between individual intentions and institutional resources, offering a robust framework for future entrepreneurship research in emerging contexts.

Practical Implications

This paper provides clear implications for policymakers in creating a more conducive environment for entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. The results highlight educational organizations' need to integrate in-depth and experiential education about entrepreneurship into their programs, moving from knowledge only to practice through simulations, cases, and projects. The significant moderating impact of Business Incubation Programs (BIP) implies the need to intensify their coverage, enhance quality, and address disparities between different regions. Governments and academe will have to focus on creating and scaling up support infrastructure such as funding, mentorship, co-working spaces, and market access. The authors encourage the government, NGOs, and private sector, or ecosystem enablers, to work together to synchronize academic learning to what society is prepared to support. Investment in public–private partnerships, incubator buildings, and inclusive innovation hubs could help to create a strong, sustainable ecosystem and recognize entrepreneurship as a credible career for Bangladeshi graduates.

Limitations and future research directions

This work provides valuable insights; however, some limitations are identified for future work. Firstly, the nature of cross-sectional design does not allow for making assumptions regarding causality; therefore, it is suggested that future research should employ longitudinal investigation to follow changes in entrepreneurial intention over time, because entrepreneurial intention is not static. It may fluctuate as students acquire new knowledge, gain practical experience, or confront real-world challenges in the labour market. Tracking students over multiple time points would capture the dynamic development of intentions. This allows researchers to assess whether early exposure to education and incubation produces lasting entrepreneurial commitment or whether its impact diminishes over time. Second, the participants are confined to Bangladeshi business students, and the future researchers should consider using students from other disciplines, institutions, and geographic locations because entrepreneurial intention may differ substantially among students from other disciplines, institutions with varying levels of resources, or regions

with distinct socio-economic conditions. Third, by concentrating on cognitive and institutional aspects (EE and BIP), the research could be insensitive to other ecosystem factors such as cultural norms, policy instruments, access to finance, and digital environment. For instance, even well-designed educational and incubation initiatives may fail to yield sustainable entrepreneurial outcomes without favourable financing opportunities or supportive cultural attitudes. Future research should systematically incorporate such ecosystem-level variables to generate richer insights into the multi-layered nature of entrepreneurial intention formation. Finally, this research was guided by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the Resource-Based View (RBV). While these frameworks are well-suited to explaining individual intention and resource-based support, they may not fully capture entrepreneurship's institutional, relational, and societal dimensions. Applying alternative theoretical lenses, such as institutional or social capital theory, could help extend the explanatory power of future studies and illuminate additional mechanisms through which entrepreneurial ecosystems shape intentions and behaviours.

Conclusion

This study highlights how Entrepreneurial Education (EE) and Business Incubation Programs (BIP) work hand in hand to shape the entrepreneurial intentions of Bangladeshi graduates. EE equips students with the knowledge and mindset to think entrepreneurially. Still, this potential becomes far more impactful when supported by incubation programs that provide mentorship, networks, and access to resources. The findings highlight the need for closer collaboration among universities, policymakers, and incubators to create an ecosystem that enables young people to pursue entrepreneurship confidently. Strengthening such partnerships offers graduates a pathway beyond traditional employment and helps unlock the creativity and entrepreneurial energy of Bangladesh's youth for the country's broader economic future.

Declarations

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Appendix: 1

Questionnaire		
Items	Entrepreneurial Education (EE)	Sources
EE1	The university provides the necessary knowledge regarding entrepreneurship.	Hasan et al. (2017)
EE2	Universities have high involvement in entrepreneurship education	
EE3	The university develops students’ skills related to entrepreneurship	
EE4	The university teaches students about entrepreneurship and starting a business	
EE5	Entrepreneurship education is mostly organized by university in our university	
EE6	I think entrepreneurship education encouraged me to become an entrepreneur.	
	Business Incubation Program (BIP)	
BIP1	The incubation center offers safe and well-equipped space for start-ups	Sahban et al. (2014)
BIP2	This incubation program provides shared facilities (labs, internet, utilities) for business activities.	
BIP3	It offers effective mentorship and technical guidance.	
BIP4	The incubation program connects start-ups with banks and government for capital and technology	
BIP5	It provides training that enhances creativity and entrepreneurial skills.	

BIP6	It collaborates with universities, government, and industry to boost growth.	
	Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)	
EI1	I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur	Liñán & Chen (2006).
EI2	My professional goal is becoming an entrepreneur	
EI3	I will make every effort to start and run my own business	
EI4	I am determined to create a business venture in the future	
EI5	I have very seriously thought in starting a firm	
EI6	I've got the firm intention to start a firm some day	